

A Survey of the Challenges Facing the Delivery of Rehabilitation Services in the Dorayi Rehabilitation Centre: Implications for Social Policy Formulation in Kano State, Nigeria.

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Abstract

This paper presents a study on survey of the challenges facing the delivery of rehabilitation services in the Dorayi Rehabilitation Centre and its implications for social policy formulation in Kano State, Nigeria. The study sought to identify the rehabilitation services offered to inmates, examine the facilities utilized in the delivery of rehabilitation services, and determine the challenges facing rehabilitation services in the Dorayi Rehabilitation Centre, Kano. The study employed a survey research design using a population of 2,333 staff and discharged inmates of the Dorayi Rehabilitation Centre, Kano. Sample for the study was derived using the table for selecting sample size by the Research Advisers (2006) in which 102 subjects were selected as sample using the proportionate cluster sampling technique. A self-developed multiple-choice questionnaire for the staff of the Dorayi Rehabilitation Centre, Kano (QSDRC) and a checklist for the facilities utilized in the delivery of the services were designed by the researcher and used for the study. The instruments were found valid and reliable at 0.64 level of coefficient. Data were analyzed using descriptive statistics in tabular forms. Findings revealed that the rehabilitation services offered to inmates in the Centre included Vocational and Psychiatric Rehabilitation, Counseling, and Literacy Education; the facilities utilized in the delivery of rehabilitation services in the Centre included Primers, Isolation rooms, Tailoring and Carpentry workshops, Gardening/orchard, and Traditional weaving materials ; and the challenges facing rehabilitation services in the Centre were shortage of facilities, inadequate programmes-content, inadequate delivery, poor administration and Staffing, low finances and lack of communal concern. The study recommended that the Kano State Government should introduce a community-based rehabilitation programme (CBRP) which will involve a joint rehabilitation service provision between government and interested voluntary agencies, including philanthropists and other members of the community; should provide facilities like ambulance and a bus, as well as medical ward with highly qualified medical personnel who will care for emergency medical cases which are highly needed for the protection of lives and enhancement of the health of both inmates and staff of the Centre; and formulate a policy that will establish and

maintain a relationship with the Kano State Zakkat and Hubsu Commission so as to enjoy extra financial support and sponsorship towards the development of the various rehabilitation programmes in the Centre.

Keywords: Rehabilitation, Social Policy, Social Welfare, Social work, and Social Welfare Policy.

Introduction

Rehabilitation has been considered a global phenomenon by many societies. In Europe, America and some parts of Asia, many rehabilitation centers have been established to provide services for the control of destitution as a necessity. According to Waddell and Burton (2004), “there has been broad agreement on the importance of rehabilitation, and the need for better occupational health and vocational rehabilitation services in the United Kingdom”, the key features of early intervention include easier access to more skilled labour, support to seek and move into work, the development of new work-focused rehabilitation programmes, and engagement of key stakeholders, and, particularly, employers and family doctors were welcomed by a wide range of organizations. However, there is considerable uncertainty about what ‘rehabilitation’ is, and about its cost-effectiveness, particularly for the common health problems that cause the most sickness, absence and long-term incapacity.

In the United States cities for instance, the victims of destitution who are the beneficiaries of rehabilitation services include people who engaged in begging which has gained recognition that the Supreme Court has ruled that, although asking people for money is a form of protected speech, restrictions on the time, place, and manner of begging are constitutional (Smith, 2005). However, in Asia, Chinese cities are among the worst beggar-devastated communities in the world (Hanchu Lu, 1999). The problem which was attributed to urban poverty and uncontrolled rural-urban migration subsided at a time for about three decades when the Communist

Government control of the rural urban drift was strict. It later exploded again when the regime softened its migration policy, and it was reported that in 1991, 28,000 beggars were arrested in the southern city of Guangzhou alone, while a total number of about 250,000 beggars across the country were reported by the China News Agency in October, 1993 (Solinger, 1998). To stem this tide, however, the Chinese Government established aid stations for indigent vagrants and beggars, as well as put in place “Detailed Implementing Rules for the Measures on the Administration of Aid to Indigent Vagrants and Beggars in cities” in 2003 (www.shanghaiCentre.com).

In Nigeria, there are many factors that necessitate the enactment, planning and introductions of social welfare policy. Among these factors includes the rapid development of populations over the decades, which resulted to unemployment among the youth, the high rate of rural to urban migration that manifested in high crimes and social problems like prostitution, squatting, begging, and destitution in the streets of towns and cities. There is also insecurity in the lives and properties of the citizens as various insurgences are reported in many parts of the country, especially the northern part of the country, which have resulted to hundreds of people becoming displaced from their various towns and villages. Women and children whose schools were burnt and destroyed by the terrorists are also among the victims of the insurgences. Many of them have been found wandering in various towns and cities looking for places to live in Kano metropolitan local government areas. The other social sectors such as health, education, transportation, housing and social security, among others, have also not adequately been funded by government. In addition to these, sound populations of people in Kano State have for long been suffering with pervasive poverty, particularly in the rural areas of the State, characterized by low income, low agricultural productivity, and food security as well as inadequate health care,

housing, education, and nutrition. This trend has led to the tendency for the rural poor to migrate to the urban sector of Kano State in the hope of securing gainful employment. The consequence is that now there is a much more serious phenomenon of poverty in both the rural and urban sectors in the State. However, the implications of this trend to this study include increase in the level of destitution among various people in Kano State. This has consequently necessitated the government designing social policies for the development of programmes in the rehabilitation institutions to solve the problem of destitution. However, a picture of the status of the social welfare services currently seems to reveal that adequate funding, efficient bureaucratic machinery and appropriately qualified staff are lacking in the social welfare sector in Nigeria.

Historically, the Extended Family Kinship System (EFS) had contributed immensely to the development of its members and the neighbourhood in the history of Kano State. However, with a high level of increase in individualism and westernization of family values, as a result of nuclearization of life, the EFS could no longer effectively protect the family and the general public in the problematic areas of their existence in the State. Family responsibility has been among the objectives of social welfare policy since the Elizabethan Poor Laws in 1601, yet the total involvement of government in the welfare system has inadvertently eroded this role of the EFS in our society. Over the years too, foreign governments and other international donor organization the UN as well as the Third-sector have been introducing and sponsoring various rehabilitation services across the continents of the world. In Africa, Nigeria is not an exception because of the several interventions involving all the tiers of government, to formulate social policies for citizens. The essence, clearly, has been to control and possibly eradicate the problems of destitution, unemployment, and urban-squalor that cause a nuisance in the towns and cities of the States across the Federation. Government in Nigerian has provided many

comprehensive rehabilitation services and programmes across states for the control of destitution. For years, there has been effective utilization of resources in the areas of social welfare service delivery. More so, the various formulated social policies employed as strategies by government in Nigeria included repatriation, rehabilitation, provision of social services, provision of employment, extra-curricular activities among children, awareness creation and propaganda. These were partly designed to alleviate the conditions of the poor but also to check the impact of their activities, agitation, grievances and nuisance to the newly emerging urban culture.

In Kano State, however, there is the Dorayi Rehabilitation Centre which was established in 1953, under the then Native Authority, during the reign of the Emir of Kano Alhaji Abdullahi Bayero. The Centre was first situated within the premises of Abdullahi Bayero College, Kano, which is today known as Bayero University Kano. Later the Centre was moved to Dorayi and taken over by the Kano State Government under the auspices of the Ministry of Social Welfare, Youth and Sports. The objectives of the Centre then, were: to provide accommodation and rehabilitation services to various categories of destitutes; to provide counseling services and Psychotherapy; to provide medication to inmates who need medical assistance; to provide and undertake repatriation of non-indigenes to their various places of origin; to provide Vocational Training, and Basic Literacy Education, and to provide Personal and Environmental Hygiene to inmates. The destitutes in the Dorayi Rehabilitation Centre, Kano, however include the cripples, blind, lepers, mentally ill persons, and drug addicts. This Centre in Kano therefore, is among the special institutions that provides active social work practice in Kano State.

Conceptual Framework

The Concept of Rehabilitation

Rehabilitation, technically, is a creative procedure which includes the cooperative intervention by various social work specialists and associates in health, technical, environmental, and other fields, to improve the physical, mental, social and vocational status of the disabled, with the objectives of preserving and improving their capacities to live happily and productively at an optimum level, and being offered similar opportunities as their neighbours (Krusen, Kottke, and Elwood 1971; Olaogun, 2007). In other words, it is a process of decreasing the dependence of the disabled person by developing, to the greatest extent possible, the abilities needed for adequate functioning in his individual situations in the local community (Helinder, 1984).

According to Sink (1979) rehabilitation is the process by which medical, psychological, social, vocational and educational services are utilized by persons with physical and or mental disabilities for the purpose of attaining maximum independence. Rehabilitation could also be said to be a generic field of practice designed to assist people with disabilities in their restoration to the fullest, physical, mental, social, vocational and economic functioning, that they are capable of attaining (Hamilton, 1950). Socially, in countries like Nigeria, rehabilitation addresses the problem of one form of disability or the other through preventing or stopping the subject from becoming or remaining as beggars.

The Concept of Social Policy

Social policy is broader concept when compare with concepts like social work and social welfare. The concept of social policy as seen as an expression of socially desirable goals which passes through legislation, institutions, and administrative programmes and practices refers to the “systematic and deliberate interventions in the social life of a country to ensure the satisfaction of the basic needs and the wellbeing of the majority of its citizens”(Aina, 1999). In contrast to

this, social policy was narrowly refers to social welfare policies. Titmus (1974) developed a comprehensive framework to analyze social policy as a subject of academic discipline, adopts such a narrow approach in which asserted that “We are concerned with the study of a range of social needs and the functioning, in condition of scarcity, of human organization, traditionally called social services or social welfare system, to meet those needs . This complex area of social life lies outside or on the fringes of the so-called free market, the mechanisms of price and test of profitability (Titmus, 1974). However, the formulation of social policies and their effective implementation are subject to complex factors. This includes government’s politics, the nation’s economy, and the global environment.

Statement of the Problem

Rehabilitation is not only concerned with physical or functional restoration or compensation of individuals disabled by injury or disease. In their work, Olaogun, Nyante, and Ajediran, (2009) stressed that attention is also given to the total quality of life in terms of wellness, happiness and satisfaction in fulfilling the demands and needs of and capabilities towards human development in terms of orientation; freedom of movement; independence; expression of self (with respect to age, sex and culture), relationship and ability to ensure independent economic existence. In other words, even after a serious injury, illness or surgery, one need to recover completely. This means that, there is the need to regain strength, to relearn skills or find new ways of doing things one did before.

The Government of Nigeria at Federal, State, and Local Government levels has made several attempts in formulating social policies and programmes to control destitution in towns, cities, and rural communities through the establishment of rehabilitation centers which are

targeted for many clients. Contemporarily, adequate resources have been effectively utilized in the provision of modern rehabilitation services aimed at restoring people's capacities to function more effectively within their living environment. Such rehabilitation services include vocational skills acquisition programmes designed for the disabled persons and catering services for women who have been abandoned caring for children.

Many other governmental policies for rehabilitation institutions such as Psychiatric Rehabilitation Centre Dawanau, Goron Dutse Remand Home and so on, in Kano State have for long been providing their own rehabilitation services to various categories of inmates. Among the rehabilitation services includes; counseling and psychotherapy, medication, repatriation, vocational training, basic literacy education, and personal and environmental hygiene. However, the Dorayi rehabilitation centre, Kano, was established before the independence of this Nation. Apart from other rehabilitation programmes taking place in psychiatric rehabilitation centres, blind centres among others, today the Dorayi rehabilitation centre is an institution which is fully engaged in the effective delivery of various services for those men and women who are found wandering in the metropolis. The aim of these services delivery is to equip individuals with appropriate skills and knowledge to fully engage in the socio-economic development of the State. In every individual, no matter the deficiency there is potentiality for some socio-economic activity. It was on this basis that the researcher conducts a survey of the challenges facing the delivery of rehabilitation services and shows its implications for policy formulation in Kano State, Nigeria.

The objectives of this study are:

- i) To identify the rehabilitation services offered to inmates in the Dorayi Rehabilitation Centre, Kano;
- ii) To examine the facilities utilized in the delivery of rehabilitation services in the Dorayi Rehabilitation Centre, Kano; and
- iii) To determine the challenges facing the delivery of the rehabilitation services in the Dorayi Rehabilitation Centre, Kano.

The following research questions are answered in this study:

- i) What are the rehabilitation services offered to inmates in the Dorayi Rehabilitation Centre, Kano?
- ii) What are the facilities utilized in the delivery of rehabilitation services in the Dorayi Rehabilitation Centre, Kano?
- iii) What are the challenges facing the delivery of the rehabilitation services in the Dorayi Rehabilitation Centre, Kano?

Methodology

This study employed a survey research design using a population of 2,333 staff and discharged inmates of the Dorayi Rehabilitation Centre. 306 subjects were derived as sample using the table for selecting sample size by the Research Advisers (2006). The subjects were captured using proportionate cluster sampling technique where the staffs were allocated 102 subjects in which sample selected was through the simple random technique. A self-developed multiple-choice questionnaire for the staff of the Dorayi Rehabilitation Centre (QSDRC) and a checklist for facilities utilized in the delivery of rehabilitation services in the Centre were used

for the study. Both instruments for this study were found valid and reliable at 0.64 level of coefficient. Data-collected were analyzed using descriptive statistics in tabular forms.

Results Presentation and Data Analysis

Research Question 1: What are the rehabilitation services offered to inmates in Dorayi Rehabilitation Centre Kano?

This research question was answered by the staff, using frequencies and percentages which are presented on the following Table 1. Where n=102

Table 1. The rehabilitation services offered to inmates in Dorayi Rehabilitation Centre Kano

The rehabilitation services offered to inmates	Options	Frequency	Percentage
Extent of Participation in the Provision of Rehabilitation Services in Dorayi Rehabilitation Centre Kano	a) Yes	102	100
	b) No	00	00
The Rehabilitation Services offered to Inmates in Dorayi Rehabilitation Centre	a) Vocational Rehabilitation	32	31.4
	b) Psychiatric Rehabilitation	26	25.5
	c) Counseling	27	26.5
	d) Literacy Education	15	14.7
	e) Others: (Psychotherapy)	2	2.0
The ways through which the Services Provided to Inmates	a) Classroom Instruction	14	13.7
	b) Clinical Nursing	15	14.7
	c) Tutelage	35	34.3
	d) Workshop Practice	34	33.3
	e) Others: (Drama and Role-playing)	4	3.9
Other Services Recommend for the Centre	a) Follow-up Services	45	44.1
	b) Community Based Rehabilitation Services	36	35.3
	c) A Joint Rehabilitation Service between the Centre and the community	21	20.6

The table 1 presents data on rehabilitation services offered to inmates in the Dorayi Rehabilitation Centre. The table shows that all the one hundred and two (102) staff respondents participated in the provision of Rehabilitation Services in the Dorayi Rehabilitation Centre Kano.

In addition to this, the above table shows that the rehabilitation services offered to inmates in the Dorayi rehabilitation Centre Kano were vocational rehabilitation (31.4%); psychiatric rehabilitation (25.5%); counseling services (26.5%); literacy education (14.7%), and psychotherapy (2%). Moreover, the table indicates that the services were provided to inmates through different methodologies, e.g. Classroom Instructions (13.7%); Clinical Nursing (14.7%); Tutelage (34.3%); Workshop Practice (33.3%); and Drama and Role-playing (3.9%).

Finally, the table above shows that all the one hundred and two (102) respondents recommended more services for the Centre; 45 (44.1%) recommended for Follow-up services; 36 (35.3%) recommended Community-Based Rehabilitation services, and (20.6%) recommended for a Joint Rehabilitation Service between the Centre and the Community.

Research Question 2: What are the facilities utilized in the delivery of rehabilitation services in Dorayi Rehabilitation Centre?

Table 2. The Checklist of Facilities Utilized in the Delivery of Rehabilitation Services in the Dorayi Rehabilitation Centre, Kano.

S/N	Facility	Availability		Number Available	Condition	
		Yes	No		Good	Bad
1	Ambulance	✓		1		✓
2	Agricultural tools	✓		53	✓	
3	Audio-visual aids	✓		5	✓	
4	Bus	✓		1		✓
5	Carpentry workshop	✓		1	✓	
6	Classrooms	✓		3	✓	
7	Computers		✓	0		
8	Counseling office	✓		2	✓	
9	Didactic materials		✓	0		
10	Electronic type-writers		✓	0		
11	First-aid kits	✓		2	✓	
12	Garden/Orchard	✓		1	✓	
13	Generator	✓		1	✓	
14	Grinding-machine	✓		1	✓	
15	Instructional materials	✓		9	✓	
16	Isolation-rooms	✓		14	✓	
17	Mechanical equipment	✓		2 set	✓	
18	Medical ward		✓	0		
19	Posters	✓		13	✓	
20	Primers	✓		27	✓	
21	Tailoring workshop	✓		1	✓	
22	Traditional weaving materials	✓		11	✓	
23	Type-writers		✓	0		
24	Workshop machinery		✓	0		

As indicated in the checklist, there was only one (1) ambulance and one (1) bus which were not in use in Dorayi Rehabilitation Centre Kano. Accordingly, there were fifty three (53) agricultural tools utilized in the Centre for the management of gardening/orchard-keeping. However, there were five (5) audio-visual aid facilities which are effectively utilized in the Centre. Other facilities like didactic materials, medical ward, electronic type-writer, computer, and workshop machinery were not provided in the Centre.

In contrast to this, however, the vocational education facilities available and properly utilized in the Centre were two (2) tailoring workshop and a carpentry workshop. Added to this, there were eleven (11) traditional weaving materials found available utilized in the Centre. In addition to this, there were fourteen (14) Isolation rooms at the Centre which were properly utilized for control of inmates who are mentally deranged.

Research Question 3: What are the challenges facing the delivery of the rehabilitation services in the Dorayi Rehabilitation Centre, Kano?

This research question was answered by staff members and analyzed using frequencies and simple percentages as shown on the following Table 3. Where n=102.

Table 3. The challenges facing the delivery of the rehabilitation services in the Dorayi Rehabilitation Centre, Kano

The challenges facing rehabilitation services	Options	Frequency	Percentage
The challenges facing the delivery of the rehabilitation services in the Dorayi Rehabilitation Centre Kano	a) Shortage of facilities	13	12.7
	b) Low programmes content	08	7.8
	c) Inadequate delivery	06	5.9
	d) Poor administration and staffing	09	8.8
	e) Low finance	49	48
	f) Others: Lack of communal concern	17	16.7

From the table above, thirteen respondents (12.7%) were of the view that one of the challenges facing the Dorayi Rehabilitation Centre, Kano, was shortage of facilities. (7.8%) reported low programmes content; six respondents (5.9%) said it was the inadequate delivery itself that was the problem; while nine respondents (8.8%) expressed poor administration and staffing. It is however important to note that, the major challenge maintained was low finance

(48%). Moreover, seventeen respondents (16.7%) were in the other category who maintained lack of communal concern for the rehabilitation programme as one of the challenges.

Summary of findings:

From the preceding data analysis, the following is the summary of findings:

- i) The rehabilitation services offered to inmates in the Dorayi Rehabilitation Centre, Kano were Vocational Rehabilitation, Psychiatric Rehabilitation, Counseling, and Literacy Education;
- ii) The facilities utilized in the delivery of rehabilitation services in the Dorayi Rehabilitation Centre, Kano were; Classrooms, Instructional materials, Primers, Counseling office, Audio-visual aids, Posters, Grinding machine, Generator, Isolation rooms, Tailoring workshop, Carpentry workshop, Gardening/orchard, Agricultural tools, Mechanical equipment, and Traditional weaving materials; and
- iii) The challenges facing rehabilitation services in the Dorayi Rehabilitation Centre, Kano were shortage of facilities, inadequate programmes-content, inadequate delivery, poor administration and Staffing, low finances and lack of communal concern.

Discussion of Results

The first finding of the study is that the rehabilitation services offered to inmates in the Dorayi Rehabilitation Centre, Kano were Vocational Rehabilitation, Psychiatric Rehabilitation, Counseling, and Literacy Education. This was however, in contrast with the rehabilitation services before independence. According to historical sources in the Dorayi Rehabilitation Centre, Kano, when it was established in 1953, under the then Native Authority during the reign of the Emir of Kano Alhaji Abdullahi Bayero, services offered to inmates included provision of Counseling and Psychotherapy, Medication, Repatriation, Vocational Training, Basic Literacy Education, and Sanitation and Health Education. During this period, there was an insufficiency

of professional workers in the Centre. Moreover, there were other rehabilitation centres in Nigeria where services were offered to inmates which differed significantly from those offered now in the Dorayi Rehabilitation Centre, Kano. Most of the Centres in the South then had been engaged in the provision of sufficient nutrition, health, vocational skills acquisition training, and counseling, among others, to inmates. Notable among such the Rehabilitation Centres in Nigeria were the Children Development Centre, Surulere, Lagos; the Stella Obasanjo Child Trust Foundation, Abuja; Atanda Olu School Surulere, Lagos; the Cheshire Home Oluyole, Ibadan; and the Rehabilitation Centre Moniya Ibadan. In addition to this, under the current welfare situation, the rise in the level of personnel in Social work practice and social welfare education as well as government involvement in the establishment of rehabilitation Centres across the States of the Federation, makes Kano State not an exception in the rehabilitation services provision. However, the Dorayi Rehabilitation Centre, Kano according to the findings of this research, is committed to offering rehabilitation services to inmates in a more comprehensive manner, through the efforts of various professionals and specialist in different fields. Relative to the Vocational Rehabilitation, Psychiatric Rehabilitation, Counseling, and Literacy Education services offered in the Dorayi rehabilitation Centre, Kano. Sabo Indabawa (2000) opined that, for the destitutes, a major recommendation was for there to be greater opportunities for basic education, with an emphasis on vocational competence. Disabled people have the same right to basic education which connotes fundamentals and reflect those aspects of behavior modification required by the individual, without which he/she would be so handicapped that he/she would be living at the periphery of the society, neither benefiting from it nor contributing to its welfare and improvement (Fafunwa, 1990).

From the second finding of the study, relative to the facilities utilized in the delivery of rehabilitation services in the Dorayi Rehabilitation Centre, Kano, viz. Classrooms, Instructional materials, Primers, Counseling office, Audio-visual aids and Posters, Grinding machine, Generator, Isolation rooms, Tailoring workshop, Carpentry workshop, Gardening/orchard, Agricultural tools, Mechanical equipment, and Traditional weaving materials. Olabiyi (2009) stress that, the most important resource, however, is the Centre itself which contains those other facilities that are necessary for the development of the positive change in the behavior of the inmates. Apart from these instructional facilities there are also other facilities such as the content of training on education and vocation/trades within the rehabilitation Centre. And this is predicated upon the goals and objectives set by the individual learner and society's course of action (Olaitan & Ali, 1997). This means that in carrying out successful vocational skills-acquisition training programmes offered in rehabilitation Centres, instructors must enable something (content) to someone (special needs learners), such that Contents can then be described as the knowledge, skills, attitudes and values to be learnt in a course, subject or lesson. Furthermore, Shehu (1996) viewed content as knowledge, skills and attitude, process and values. Therefore Knowledge analyzed as facts, explanations, principles and definitions, skill and process of reading, writing, calculating, and values as concerned with good and bad, right and wrong, beautiful and ugly. In other words, contents are the subject matter to be taught by the trainer to the trainees (special needs learners). However, the facilities utilized in the delivery of rehabilitation services in the Dorayi Rehabilitation Centre, Kano, according to the findings of this research work, include the facilities earlier-mentioned. Considering that behavior modification is consequent upon the results of counseling services offered to inmates in rehabilitation Centres, Okorie (2000) argues that "skills comprise two general components: the

knowledge component and the activity component.” The activity component is made up of motor and perceptual skills, both knowledge and activity components combined in different proportions for different skills. The knowledge component is however, a practical or activity components of skills related to those areas of knowledge which pertains to the mode of doing. This is, however, the effect of counseling the inmates in the rehabilitation Centre and this enables special needs learners to acquire know-how of a variety of skills that are related to vocations. Theory and practice must be fully be integrated into a teaching-learning process for the purpose of effectiveness and worthwhile results. All teaching should help special needs learners acquire a blend of theory and practice in order to achieve their objectives. This will help teacher/instructor in a logical plan of his teaching and also help the special needs learners see the relationship between the units and sub units thereby enhancing comprehension of learners.

With regard to the challenges facing the delivery of the rehabilitation services in the Dorayi Rehabilitation Centre, Kano, such as shortage of facilities, low programmes content, inadequate delivery, poor administration and staffing, low finances, and lack of communal concern, most of the personnel who participated in the delivery of the rehabilitation services viewed one of the greatest challenges facing the Centre as low finances. Most of the facilities in the Centre are very old, and this is another challenge facing the Centre. Also apart from the fact that the facilities are out-dated, they are equally not enough for effective services delivery. The Centre as a facility also lacks modern infrastructural facilities to segregate the inmates, according to their peculiarities. Moreover, facilities, like dispensary and psychiatric asylums are not arranged satisfactorily. Also to the method of delivery, however, the challenge facing the Centre include that individuals needed to be treated following an adequate assessment of problems. As such, when delivering any rehabilitation service, there is the need for the Centre to pre-empt the

method of delivery by making an appropriate assessment of the inmate and full consideration of the service needed. This, also, implies the challenge facing the Centre as to programme content; the contents for programmes are haphazardly formulated for inmates without streamlining them into sections on the basis of the needs of the inmates. Moreover, a very important challenge facing the rehabilitation services is in the administration and the dominance of poorly qualified staff. In the administration, too much bureaucracy is involved in deciding favorably for services of the Centre. This involves disparate functionaries from the Ministry for Women and Social Development, the State Emergency Relief and Rehabilitation Agency (KSERERA), and the internal Dorayi Rehabilitation Centre, Kano administration. This brings about a problem of administration in clashes of authority for the entire rehabilitation services delivery system of the Centre. In addition to this, many staffs are not adequately professionally trained in rehabilitation services delivery. In the final analysis, problems connected to poor performances, poor content, and inadequate methods may result to frequent set-backs in the entire programme.

Conclusion and Recommendation

This study has proven that the most disturbing phenomenon across urban cities of our contemporary world is destitution. This phenomenon has become a nuisance to our cities and a common feature of this problem contemporarily is begging by various individuals. There are many socio-cultural trends and beliefs in the process of falling into destitution by many people across Nigeria, but in Kano State, one of the areas in the North-Western part of Nigeria, many scholars are convinced that begging in the streets highly implicates religious and traditional beliefs systems. These also relate with conditions that cause poverty among the constituents of destitution in urban cities. More appalling is that what is collected through the begging is not even enough for their needs. Thus, instead of them to work towards earning what can satisfy their needs, they end up roaming the streets, and sometimes sleeping under bridges. This study

therefore has implications for social policy formulation in Kano State and Nigeria at large due to the fact that it contributes immensely to the development of knowledge on rehabilitation services and social policy planning formulation and implementation. As such it serves as a knowledge based document that provides information on various services which can be utilized by Government of Kano State to formulate social policies that will be appropriately utilize for effective social development in the State.

The study recommended that:

- i) The Kano State Government should formulate social policy that will guide a community-based rehabilitation programme (CBRP) which will involve a joint rehabilitation service provision between government and interested voluntary agencies, including philanthropists and other members of the community. The aim here is to utilize both economic and social resources of the community in effectively solving the problems of discharged inmates, so that they can resettle, and by extension the entire community;
- ii) The government of Kano State should also provide facilities like ambulance and a bus, as well as medical ward with highly qualified medical personnel who will care for emergency medical cases which are highly needed for the protection of lives and enhancement of the health of both inmates and staff of the Centre. Moreover, more modern tools for the development of skills among the inmates should also be provided in the Centre. A very crucial helping regime which is needed in the Centre is empowerment of the inmates when they are about to be discharged from the Centre. And this can only be gained through the provision of capital, money, and linking of the discharged inmates already established workshops and enterprises within the

- community; and there is need for education and mobilization of voluntary agencies and Non-governmental organizations to come to the aid of government in providing financial and other assistance to the Centre so as to further support and boost its activities; and
- iii) The Kano State Government should also formulate a social policy that will establish and maintain a relationship with the Kano State Zakkat and Hubsu Commission so as to enjoy extra financial support and sponsorship towards the development of the various rehabilitation programmes in the Centre.

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